

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND EXISTING PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The report discusses the important role of scientific and innovative developments in the development of the green economy and the problems of their implementation. It discusses ways to eliminate shortcomings and makes recommendations.*

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The development of each country, its place and influence on the world stage, is, of course, determined by the development of its economic situation and the widespread application of advanced examples of science and technology. The Republic of Uzbekistan is becoming one of the leading countries in the East. The reforms and fundamental changes taking place in the country, along with the introduction of new technologies and equipment into industrial enterprises, pose a number of strategic issues and problems for state administration.

Unlike some imperialist countries, all the work being done in Uzbekistan is aimed at raising the well-being, interests and social status of the people to a higher level. The social situation of the population, which has recently become a global problem, the large-scale development of technical equipment and advanced solutions in the field of construction in the field of housing supply, on the one hand, are widely welcomed by the population, but on the other hand, they cause a number of other problems, in addition to the ecological point of view. In order for the work done to be effective, it is advisable to analyze the negative and positive aspects of the work being done, as well as to work on finding solutions to the emerging problems and implementing them.

Innovative technologies are clearly and indisputably proven to be useful for industry, facilitating human labor, improving their lifestyle, and contributing to the development of the country. However, only if they are used effectively their role will become incomparable and be widely implemented in life. Otherwise, due to the slowness of their practical application, a number of innovative solutions either remain on paper or, being applied in isolation, their effectiveness is ignored.

We will give a couple of real examples to prove our point. One of the main factors of a green economy is the widespread use of alternative energy sources that are clean from an ecological point of view [1-3]. However, a positive solution to this problem has not yet been implemented in our country on a large scale. Thanks to the trips of the country's leader to foreign countries and the successes of non-traditional energy production methods that have been used there for several years, and thanks to their initiatives, through a number of Resolutions and Orders [4,5], the construction of the first power plants, which were pioneers for our country, began. At a time

when the most urgent issue of energy shortage is looming, it is urgent to identify which problem is preventing this shortage from being filled and to work on its solution.

Let us dwell on the problem itself. It is known that the most promising alternative energy source currently available is solar energy [1]. We will not dwell on the unprecedented value of solar energy. This issue has been repeatedly discussed in all publications. However, the conversion of solar energy into electricity is carried out using photovoltaic elements made of semiconductor materials [6]. It is well known that the useful efficiency of solar elements (SE) is currently unsatisfactory. In addition, there are a number of problems in their exploitation, as a result of which we need highly qualified personnel who can solve them on the spot. Physicists are specialists who understand the principle of operation of SEs and can analyze the electrophysical processes occurring in their volume. However, this professional knowledge is not enough to understand and solve engineering problems. For specialists in the energy sector, there is no single discipline that teaches about the properties of semiconductor materials, the processes of converting photons into energy in them, the relationship between the useful work coefficient and the operating environment. Power engineers, if there are malfunctions in the operation process, cannot find an effective solution through independent action.

Another of the same problems is that the rapid introduction of electronics, microelectronics and microprocessor-based technical equipment into the enterprises of this industry requires innovative proposals for modern personnel training and management. After all, it is natural that breakdowns and failures occur during the operation of semiconductor materials and electronic equipment. Their on-site repair and uninterrupted implementation of the technological process are important for the enterprise's rating.

The third problem is the slow modernization of teaching in technical universities where engineers are trained. Because, no matter how much science teachers improve their skills, there are still few useful aspects of pedagogical technologies. Because most scientists in the field of pedagogy are graduates of pedagogical universities and have developed new interactive methods for school teachers or students of humanities courses. There are very few interactive methods that have a balanced position for technical universities. This makes it difficult for students of technical universities to easily understand the processes occurring inside the emerging microelectronics and nanoelectronics devices. Therefore, it is necessary for technical teachers to include in the teaching process precisely those subjects that reveal the processes of obtaining electricity from alternative energy sources and are well mastered by students. In such studies, it is very important to expand and implement the recommendations developed by engineering educators with many years of pedagogical experience.

As proof of our idea, let us talk about the interactive method developed by the authors of [7]. In this study, the need for students of the energy sector to study the physics of semiconductors in depth and, relying on the theory of similarity in mastering this science, the movement of electrons occurring in the volume of semiconductors is illustrated by the newly developed interactive method "Army of Electrons". In it, the student, in essence, imagines himself in the army, engaged in activities where physical strength is important, and explains them with the results of their mutual movements, collisions, energy exchanges, and the struggles (energy exchanges) of military personnel, which are practically understandable to everyone (see Figure 1).

Such an explanation is consistent with the requirements of new pedagogical technologies for making lessons playful or interesting, and the concept of military service is familiar to everyone, and the ideas about the role of force (energy) are clarified.

Figure 1. View of colliding electrons. a) collision of electrons of equal energy, b) oblique collision of electrons of equal energy, c) vector diagram of electron collision, d) explanation of electrons as a military battle using the theory of similarity.

The issue of management and personnel training at enterprises is also an urgent issue. However, unfortunately, the use of old, morally and structurally unusable equipment is still common. Since the head of the enterprise is not innovative and does not take the initiative, our country will lag behind in development. Innovations are created, but their fate does not go beyond paper. In conclusion, while we are working with innovative research, we should not forget that we also need to work on the problems that prevent their wider application in practice. We have a number of proposals in this regard, and work is underway to implement them.

REFERENCES

1. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Солнечная_энергетика;
2. <https://www.renwex.ru/ru/ii/solnechnaya-ehnergetika/>
3. <https://solara.uz/ru/blog/ispolzovaniye-solnechnoy-energii-v-uzbekistane-ustoychivoye-budushcheye>;
4. Постановление президента республики узбекистан «О мерах по развитию возобновляемой и водородной энергетики в республике Узбекистан» г. Ташкент, 9 апреля 2021 г., № ПП-5063.
5. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 30 апреля 2021 года № УП-6218 «О мерах по комплексной систематизации национальной базы законодательства».
6. https://www.radioradar.net/hand_book/documentation/sun_bat.html
7. A.M.Kasimakhunova, M.A.Shakhodjayev , The effectiveness of interactive methods in teaching solar energy in higher and vocational educational institutions.